

Measurement of Consumer Attitude: Purchase of Green Products

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ABSTRACT

Population over explosion made consumer's life havoc in satisfying their needs. Consumers are in search of new versions of natural products to protect their health. Corporates are run with commercializing the products with more concern with production and packaging. They are in strategic point to attract consumers towards their new package of green products with in and out spoken messages of environment protection and consumer health well being. Many corporate giants imbibe "Green Marketing" practices which it refers to holistic marketing concept wherein the production, market consumption and disposal of products and services happen in a manner that is less detrimental to the environment. With growing importance of green products usage, this investigation put insight to know the consumer attitude, key issues of green products and influential factors on consumer to purchase green products are measured. The test results envisage female respondents are more conscious about the purchase of green products. The price of the products, packaging, labeling, friends and relatives are the significantly influencing factors.

Keywords: *Green Marketing, Green products, Consumer attitude*

1. Introduction

Rapid economic growth paves the way in increasing consumer consumption worldwide. This turn causes environmental weakening through over-consumption and importance of natural resources. The consequences of environmental degradation are global

warming, depletion of stratospheric ozone layer, pollution of sea and rivers, noise and light pollution, acid rain and desertification (Ramlogan, 1997). Grunert (1993) reported that about 40% of environmental degradation has been brought about by the consumption activities of private households. As the environment continues to deteriorate, it has become a persistent public concern in developed countries. Furthermore, it has also awakened developing countries to the green movement for the preservation of the environment. Consumer attitudes are a composite of a consumer beliefs, emotions and behavioral intentions toward some object--within the context of marketing, usually a brand or retail store. These components are viewed together since they are highly interdependent and together represent forces that influence how the consumer will react to the object.

Creating customer satisfaction and building long-term profitable customer relationship are some of the primary objectives firms try to achieve to sustain their businesses in the competitive business world. With an increase in the social and political pressures, many firms embraced green marketing strategies and exploited these environmental issues as a source of competitive advantage. Profit driven firms are usually motivated to adopt the concept of green marketing in their businesses provided that consumers demonstrate a high degree of environmental attitude and hence translate this into environmental friendly purchasing commitment. Hence many companies started to be more socially responsive in addressing pollution and waste disposal by developing environmentally friendly packaging and putting in numerous efforts to

keep in-step with the environmental movement. However, some of the greatest challenges faced by these firms are changes in consumer preferences, suspicion of green advertising claim, critical consumer perception of green products and the high cost invested in developing green products. As a result, it is vital to explore how consumers view the environmental issues, and how they behave, especially in their attitudes towards green products or environmentally friendly products.

2. Review of Literature

Economics reveals how the people use their limited resources to try to satisfy unlimited wants (McTaggart, Findlay & Parkin 1992, 24, cited in Polanski, 1994). Current times, environmental concern is rising rapidly as an essential topic for consumers because of global warming (Chen, 2010). Both individual and industrial are becoming concerned about the environment. Dodds, John (2006) observed that harnessing the consumer's power gives a positive effect in changing the environment. The so-called "green consumer" movement in the US and other countries help them to reach the critical mass and all this directly affect the shoppers' minds effectively. This study helps us in knowing that how consumers transform to green consumers. Hans, Jim (2007) noted that green marketers have taken the advantage of confusion prevailing in the market place among the consumers' minds. They purposely make false or exaggerate green claims. Following the same logic, it becomes possible to argue that green marketing leads to fantasy

in the world where consumers need eco-friendly environment.

D'Souza et al. (2007) stated that demographics tend to play an important role in regards both the interest of green product and green certification. Green Trade & Development (2008) discussed that consumers are said to be changing their attitude and perception and profess a strong willingness in favor of the eco-friendly environment. This concept helps us in realizing a fact that how much a consumer is conscious about their environment.

3. Research design

This study is proposed to know the consumer's attitude on green products related to gender concern with measurable key aspects that determines the opinion of the respondents. More over this study focused on to evolve the factors influencing the purchase of green products.

This investigation find out the consumer attitude towards green products covered; Tea bags, Electronics and FMCG products. Respondent opinion has collected through structured questionnaire. Secondary data is viewed through website published articles; focus group transcript, news paper and relevant journals etc. mainly to highlight the conceptual analysis of eco-friendly products. The sampling technique involved is convenient sampling. The sample size is 156; respondents are selected from the district of Vizianagaram.AP.

4. Consumer Attitude on Green Products: Gender related

Table 1: The opinion of gender is varied. Respondents attitude on green products are given below.

S. No	Aspects	Mean Score		Total	t-statistics	Significance (p – value)
		M	F			
1.	Lesser harm to the environment	4.22	4.47	4.34	8.894	.003
2.	Health Conscious	4.29	4.66	4.47	1.771	.185
3.	Conserve energy and water	3.43	3.71	3.57	3.934	.049
4.	Green product protect environment	3.71	4.18	3.94	20.615	.000
5.	Recyclable / Reusable	3.50	4.00	3.75	1.757	.187
6.	Essential for better future	3.72	4.59	4.15	14.121	.000
7.	Easy to dispose	4.14	4.29	4.21	25.017	.000
8.	Made of eco-friendly material	3.64	4.24	3.94	14.100	.000
9.	Lack of awareness about their uses	3.46	3.98	3.72	.523	.427
10.	There is lack of demand	4.00	4.04	4.02	11.207	.001
11.	Non availability in market	3.42	3.47	3.44	19.699	.000
12.	Over priced	3.47	4.32	3.89	5.414	.021

13.	Beneficial investment in long run	3.60	4.15	3.87	19.947	.000
14.	Ecological requirement not for marketing strategy	3.56	3.67	3.61	31.255	.000

5. Respondent Opinion on Green Products

Respondent's opinions on green products evaluate with fourteen variables are explained in table one. The appropriateness of this analysis is estimated with the help of Kaiser Meyer Olkin (KMO) and Bartlett's Test of sphericity and the results are shown below.

Table 2: KMO and Bartlett's Test

KMO Measure of sampling adequacy and Bartlett's Test of sphericity	0.792
Application of Chi-Square value	759.210
Degrees of freedom (df)	91.000
Significance	.000

The KMO value is very high (0.792). Similarly, Bartlett's Test rejects the null hypothesis that the variables are not related as the approximate chi-square value is 759.210 at 91 degrees of freedom which is significant at five percent level. Therefore, the factor analysis may be considered as an appropriate technique.

Table 3: Presented below gives the rotated component matrix table count by using varimax method which is used to assign factors that have higher loadings

Sl. No.	Attitudes			Component
	(F1)	(F2)	(F3)	(F4)
1.	Essential for better future			.817
2.	Recyclable / Reusable			.792
3.	Over priced			.781
4.	Lack of awareness about their uses			.736
5.	Beneficial investment in long run			.675
6.	Made of eco-friendly material			.626
7.	Health Conscious			.621
8.	Ecological requirement not for marketing strategy			.883
9.	Non availability in market			.861
10.	Lesser harm to the environment			.738
11.	Conserve energy, water			.590
12.	Green product protect environment			.581
13.	There is lack of demand			.753
14.	Easy to dispose			.696

Source: Computational data

Table 4: The finding of the principal component analysis which is used to extract the number of variables by using the Eigen value is given below.

PCA variance	Key aspects	Number of variables	Eigen value	Percent variation	Cumulative percent
1.	F1	7	4.3220	30.874	30.874
2.	F2	2	2.1680	15.483	46.356
3.	F3	3	1.1580	8.269	54.626
4.	F4	2	1.1098	7.846	62.471

The four factors can be extracted which amount to the cumulative percentage of 62.471 percent. Thus four factors which are keys to determining the opinion of the respondents about green products are extracted from fourteen aspects. The first factor has seven variables with the high factor loading of 0.817 named as "future resort". The second factor is the two variables with the high factor loading of 0.883 named as "marketing

strategy”. The third factor is the three variables with the high factor loading of 0.738 named as “eco friendly” and the final factor is the two variables with the high factor loading of 0.753 named as “use of way”. These four aspects of variables play an important role in determining the consumer attitude of the respondents towards green products.

6. Factors Influence: Purchase of Green Products

Table 5: In the purchasing of green products, by consumer the influencing factors are explained.

Sl. No.	Attributes of product	Mean Score		Average Mean Score	t-value	p-value
		Male	Female			
1.	Product Price	3.85	3.95	3.90	13.754	.000
2.	Green attribute of the products quality	3.49	4.09	3.79	1.747	.188
3.	Environment Consciousness	4.26	4.66	4.46	4.462	.036
4.	Advertisement	4.26	4.64	4.45	7.127	.008
5.	Influence of friends and relatives	3.78	3.94	3.86	50.864	.000
6.	Packaging & Labeling	3.28	3.86	3.57	79.995	.000
7.	Benefits of green products	4.26	4.66	4.46	4.462	.036
Average score		3.88	4.25			

Source: Field Data

Table 5 reveals that the consumers are more influenced to purchase green products by the awareness created by the friends and relatives and the attractive packaging. In this study is to reveal that the female respondents are more conscious about the purchase of green products. The price of the products, packaging labeling and influence by friends and relatives are the significantly influencing factors.

7. Discussion

On gender base analysis supported that most of the female respondent behavior are inclined to purchase green products because they are health conscious towards the family. All the aspects of variables given strength to the (Table 1, 5) attitude measurement. In this situation the more awareness programs are conducted in every stage of people is better for future. This study suggests that consumer’s opinion on green products is very high. But in case the lack of demand for green products is low (0.753). The corporate should focus on more eco friendly products to create awareness on green products for the consumer’s usage. The green products packaging level is a concern area (3.57) need of the hour to change type of packaging to attract more consumers to purchase the products.

8. Conclusion

Business organizations are adopting go green policy on production to process and packaging. Business is engineered back the need of the eco-friendly civilization. Corporates redesigned strategic approach as green marketing to grow; it may involve start-up costs and on save money in the long term. Therefore, in the green product strategy, marketer focus on customer needs and wants to develop Consumer Attitude towards Green Products. The consumers are willing to buy the green products, but the lack of awareness of green products is high. In this time the marketers are voluntarily willing to educate the consumers are more important. Marketers find an opportunity to improve product’s performance and support customer’s reliability and authority a higher price. They produce more environmentally responsible packages. (Recycle, biodegradable, reuse), and ensure that products meet or exceed the quality hope of customers.

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